

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

Co-creation Workshop Report Pan-European Workshop

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1. General information and preparatory activities

1.1 Organisational details and achievements

Organisational details and achievements	Description
Organiser(s)	Wageningen University (WU) – Lead organiser Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL (Q-PLAN)
Date of the workshop	14 October 2021
Platform / digital tools used	MS Teams (incl. MS Teams online polls)
No of participants (SRG members and experts)	14 + 1
No of participants (MAP + team members)	32
Duration of workshop (hours)	3
No of good practices ranked	N/A (Not in the scope of the event)
No of barriers and solutions co-defined	N/A (Not in the scope of the event)
No of new business models co-created	N/A (Not in the scope of the event)
Report Authors	
No	Team members name
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1.2 Methodology and overview of preparatory activities

Following the regional co-creation workshops organised in the 12 Beacon Regions of the projects, the pan-European workshop was organised on **October 14th, 2021**, involving the members of the Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG). This 3-hour online workshop aimed at validating and expanding the results of the regional events, as well as to discuss the European dimension of the potential for the development of Short Food Supply Chains and, finally, to identify potential trends across countries that would support the replicability of the tools and solutions developed by the agroBRIDGES consortium.

The event was organised by WU with close support from Q-PLAN, the partner responsible for the management of the SRG and Task 1.6 Leader. During the organisation phase, the workshop agenda, invitations, and workshop materials such as presentations and structure were agreed between the two partners. The two partners opted for the Microsoft Teams teleconference platform as the means of workshop implementation.

A save-the-date email was sent to all invitees at least one month prior to the event, followed up by an official invitation two weeks before the event, including a registration form, the workshop agenda, and the session links to attend the workshop. In this event the SRG members of the project, comprising 12 representatives of MAPs groups – one per Beacon Region, the Experts Advisory Board of the project and experts involved in relevant EU initiatives, projects, and institutions – were invited. Partners from the “sister” projects involved in the agroBRIDGES Joint Clustering activities of Task 6.2 (EU projects funded under the RUR-05-2020 call) were also invited to attend, along with the members of the agroBRIDGES consortium.

In total, **32 participants** attended the pan-European workshop¹, including **14 members of the SRG** (70% of total SRG members), **17 consortium partners** and **1 representative of the sister projects** (COACH). The breakdown of SRG members who joined and contributed to the event is as follows:

- 1 Advisory Board member
- 3 EU experts
- 10 representatives of the regional MAPs (Denmark, Turkey, Greece, Finland, Poland - 2, Latvia, Lithuania, France and Italy)

The workshop was supported by a four-member team (2 from WU and 2 from Q-PLAN). Q-PLAN presented the project, workshop objectives and the project findings to kickstart the conversation and brainstorming. The reporting of workshop outcomes was led by WU and Q-PLAN supported. The moderation of the conversations, co-creation activities and digital tools was performed by WU.

The pan-European workshop was organised in the following structure:

- **Introductory session**

During this session, workshop participants were welcomed by workshop organisers and were briefly introduced to the project, its activities and objectives, as well as to the role and functions of the SRG by the Project Coordinator. This session ended with WU providing a short overview of the workshop, its agenda and expected structure to guide participants through the event.

- **Tour-de-table of participants**

During this session, all workshop attendees (internal and external to the consortium) were introduced to each other through short presentation of themselves.

- **Session 1 – Barriers in the development of SFSCs and proposed solutions to mitigate them**

The first core session of the European co-creation workshop focused on the topic of barriers in the development of SFSCs and proposed solutions. Q-PLAN presented to participants the outcomes of the analysis of the regional co-creation workshop results, as presented in Table 5 of Chapter 4. Short polls interrupted the presentation in several points, to ask participants to express their opinion. Six polls were implemented. In the first poll, stakeholders were asked to vote among the five barrier categories identified in regional level. The rest of the polls requested participants to indicate the most effective solutions for mitigating barriers, one poll for each of the five categories.

¹ The full participants list from the pan-European workshop is available upon request.

- **Session 2 – Business and marketing models for SFSCs**

In this session, the discussions and brainstorming focused on new and improved business models for SFSCs. First, Q-PLAN briefly presented the business models stemming from the business modelling session of the regional co-creation workshops, as presented in Table 6 of Chapter 4 in this report. The presentation concluded with the key trends in business models coming from the analysis of regional results (Table 7, Chapter 4) as well as the key determining factors for SFSC business model development (Table 8, Chapter 4). An open discussion was planned after the presentation of business models, prompting attendees to identify additional elements for SFSC business models, and to pinpoint elements that might enhance the replicability of these business models.

- **Session 3 – Marketing strategies and Unique Selling Points (USPs) for SFSCs**

In the third and final session of the workshop, marketing strategies and USP of SFSCs were the main focus. Q-PLAN opened the session with a brief presentation of the insights and references made to marketing issues by regional MAP members. The presentation served as an inspiration for an open discussion among the stakeholders, inviting them to propose additional ideas and suggestions for supporting farmers' and producers marketing strategy and how to diversify the messages and communication for different target audiences.

- **Closing session**

After the end of the co-creation exercises, closing remarks were made about the discussions that took place through the event and participants were informed about future activities of the project, in which their contribution is welcomed. The workshop organisers, WU and Q-PLAN thanked participants for their time and contribution to the project.

After the end of the workshop, a “thank-you” email was sent by the lead organiser, WU, to all invitees including those who did not attend, along with the presentations of the workshop and an invitation to register to the agroBRIDGES Online MAP Forum, to continue the discussions started during the workshops.

The pan-European workshop agenda circulated to workshop participants is provided in Annex III.

2. Co-creation results

2.1 Session 1 - Barriers and solutions

This session started with an introduction of the main barriers to SFSC development and solutions to these barriers that were identified in the regional co-creation workshops. Participants were then asked to identify the main (general) barriers and (specific) solutions to these barriers. The session ended with an open discussion on barriers or solutions that may have been missed in the results from the regional co-creation workshops. Participants were also asked whether any barriers or solutions needed to be addressed at an EU level. For this latter question, no specific points were raised by the participants.

The ranking of the main barriers and solutions was done using polls, immediately after the presentation of a specific result. The first poll followed the presentation of the five main categories of barriers impeding the development of SFSCs. Workshop participants were instructed to choose a maximum of 2 of the following options, each corresponding to a main barrier category: (i) Business Operations, (ii) Use of technology, (iii) Commercialisation, (iv) Business growth, and (v) Legislation and Policies. 21 responses were submitted in this poll and Business Operations was identified by participants as the most important barrier in SFSC development with 31% of votes casted. The following figure shows the results of this polls as displayed in MS Teams after the poll closed. Participants were able to see the results in real time.

Figure 1: Result of poll "What is the main barrier to SFSCs in Europe?"

Following this poll, specific barriers within each of the five main categories were presented to workshop participants, along with suggested solutions proposed by MAP members during the regional co-creation workshops. Five polls were launched in-between the presentation of the barriers and solutions in each main category. Participants, this time, were requested to select the best solutions among those proposed. Multiple votes were given to each participant, but no more than three. The poll results were visible to participants in real time. The following table summarises the polls results.

Table 1: Suggested solutions per barrier category (voting results)

Barrier type	Proposed solution(s)
Business Operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Cooperation networks, partnerships and collective actions
Use of technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Training to improve digital skills and competences of producers and farmers
Commercialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Cooperation between suppliersImproved accessibility of SFSC in urban areas
Business growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Networking events, platforms for knowledge exchange, matching of potential partners and brokerage events implemented by regional clusters, hubs and agri-food networks
Legal and regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Regulatory package including directives, norms and protocols for SFSC implementation

As shown in Figure 8, addressing barriers related to business operations is best done through improved cooperation networks, partnerships and collective actions, with 24 out of 38 votes (42%) casted supporting this. The next best solution was resource sharing [among actors in SFSCs], concentrating 31% of participants' votes.

Figure 2: Results of poll "Which is the best solution for solving barriers related to SFSC business operations?"

Provision of training to improve digital skills and competences of producers and farmers was the most preferred solution for technology-related barriers (31% of total votes). A second option, albeit with a large difference in votes from the first, was the implementation of technology testing, mediation and troubleshooting sessions among farmers and trusted experts and technology providers (22% of total votes).

Figure 3: Results of poll “Which is the best solution to address barriers related to SFSC use of technologies?”

On the topic of barriers for commercialisation, options such as the cooperation between suppliers and improved accessibility of SFSCs in urban areas were deemed by participants as the most appropriate solutions (26% and 24% of the votes, respectively).

Figure 4: Results of poll “What is the best solution to address SFSC barriers to commercialisation?”

Networking events, platforms for knowledge exchange, matching of potential partners and brokerage events implemented by regional clusters, hubs and agri-food networks were the proposed solutions to mitigate barriers related to business growth of SFSCs (26% of the votes).

Figure 5: Results of poll "What is the best solution to address barriers for business growth?"

Finally, the preferred solutions to barriers for SFSCs stemming from regulations and legislation was the creation of a regulatory package including directives, norms and protocols towards the implementation of SFSC models (Table 7, 32% of the votes). The rest of the options provided tied in the second position.

Figure 6: Results of poll "What is the best solution to overcome barriers from regulations / policies?"

In the discussion that followed, several participants emphasised that a lack resources, represent a crucial barrier to SFSC. This barrier may present itself at the level of the producer, who may lack key knowledge or skills, but also more broadly at the level of the workforce as a whole, where the lack of trained labour can be an impediment to further development of an SFSC. Solutions to this barrier were discussed in the form of

collaborations, for instance, between producers and other chain actors such as distributors. The necessary human, financial or know-how resources that may be missing at the producer level could then be complemented by resources at other chain levels. Collaborations may also move beyond chain actors to include not only groups of entrepreneurs and the workforce but also connections to tourism operators, for example.

Some points of caution were also raised during the discussion. First, that barriers / solutions may not be the same for all types of SFSC. For instance, SFSC for processed products may be much more difficult to establish than SFSC for fresh products such as fruits and vegetables. This is not only because of the nature of the supply chain, since it includes more stages by definition, but also because controls, food safety issues and 'selling the story' to the consumer about a processed product can be more difficult. Furthermore, if producers interact with larger manufacturing companies, it is necessary to ensure that they benefit from processing and distribution. Therefore, fair forms of cooperation need to be found. Another note was that SFSCs do not by definition lead to benefits for producers and that local food chains do not necessarily mean that there are no (or only few) intermediaries. The types of SFSC business models will be further discussed in the following section.

2.2 Session 2 – SFSC business and marketing models

This session started with an introduction of the types of SFSC business models, their characteristics, and the key success factors of SFSC business models that were identified in the regional co-creation workshops. This was followed by an open discussion in which participants were asked to add business model types, characteristics or key success factors and discuss these more generally.

Concerning the types of business models that were presented, several participants pointed towards the overlap between categories and the difficulty of placing some types in a specific, well-defined category. One of the participants suggested that there could be a hybrid category of SFSC types. This category would include the models that do not fit a single category because they combine different aspects of specific types, and some actors may also use different parts of different business models.

Several participants also referred to the business model characteristics related to sustainability outcomes and pointed out that these seemed to be focused primarily on economic (and environmental) sustainability outcomes. The business model focus of this session may explain this. However, alternative SFSCs are not necessarily developed for profits and social aspects may also be important to consider when discussing SFSC models. An example was given of a social food chain where public land is being used to produce food for solidarity associations / poor people in the city. While such social SFSCs may exist in some places, they may not be that common elsewhere. One participant expressed doubts about the viability of the social model and argued that first economic viability should be achieved, before the focus can be relayed to the environmental or social dimension. Furthermore, the social model may also face resistance in some regions or from some parties because it requires a high level of trust in governance based on democratic principles or cooperative-like structures.

Related to the critical success factors, one participant pointed towards the large diversity in SFSC models, even within the groups that were identified in the presentation. Conditions for success may therefore also be very different for different types, and the governance / transparency of the models needs to be considered as a success factor too.

Several participants saw a key opportunity for SFSC that can be further explored, namely, SFSC deliveries to public procurement, e.g., for school canteens. This was seen as an opportunity in line with the message that is coming out of the EU “Farm to Fork” strategy which emphasises the need for sustainable food production and the necessity of collaboration as a way forward. At the same time, the difficulty of SFSC inclusion in public procurement was also emphasised, for instance, in the case of access to hospital canteens (in Italy). This will be discussed further in the following section, where unique selling points and marketing strategies are presented, and a discussion evolved about different strategies for different target audiences.

2.3 Session 3 – Unique selling points and marketing strategies for SFSCs

The session started with presenting the unique selling points (USP) and marketing strategies (MS) of SFSCs that were derived from the regional co-creation workshops. Next, participants discussed additional USP and MS. Attention was also paid to USP and MS that could target different stakeholders and audiences. Some more general points were also made by the participants that are useful as an input to the following steps of the project.

A main discussion point that came up in this session related to the segmentation of consumers of SFSC. One participant pointed out that social science research generally shows that more sustainable food products (and in extension SFSC products) are more likely to be bought by more affluent, better educated consumers. When thinking of unique selling points, and marketing strategies, this should be kept in mind. A similar segmentation could be thought of in terms of urban versus rural consumers, where certain (lower) social classes are more likely to be found in urban areas. Another participant added to this point by suggesting a broad classification of consumer segments (for which targeted MS could be developed) as rural - urban - institutional buyers - non-profits. The following figure illustrates the customer segmentation proposed by participants with respect to the targeting of marketing strategies, unique selling points and communication messages.

Figure 7: Target audiences of SFSC marketing strategies and USPs

Different marketing strategies could then target different segments. For instance, farmers’ markets in rural areas could allow farmers to directly sell the story of their product; digital platforms could deliver these messages also to urban consumers; non-profits could be targeted by a message such as ‘buying food for a good cause’ etc. A note was made that agroBRIDGES intends to develop such digital tools for delivering marketing messages.

Several participants contributed to a discussion on the ‘message’ that SFSC should be delivering. One participant argued that we talk too easily about food quality in the context of SFSCs, but SFSCs should be seen as a way to open the box of what quality of food really means. Bringing this across to consumers is much more complex for processed products and meat products than for fresh products, for example. Another participant saw an opportunity of using public procurement, especially through school canteens, as a way to ‘educate’ consumers about the implications of food choices and sustainable food in general. Through school meals, both children and parents can be targeted in delivering the message and increasing awareness. A note was made that a tool will be developed in agroBRIDGES with this specific focus.

An extensive discussion followed on whether the message for SFSCs should include references to health attributes of SFSC products. Opinions were divided. Some participants worried that health claims could not be substantiated (proven) and hence should not be used. It could be better to focus on (clear) benefits for the producer such as higher margins or a better position in the chain; and possibly also extend this to social aspects such as preventing abandonment of rural areas. A suggestion was made to include producers more in research and development activities so that they can contribute to developing new messages. Furthermore, the “story that is being sold” could also be different for different target audiences. For example, health claims may be more important for more affluent consumers, while an economic story may be more important to attract poorer households. An interesting observation was made that local identity should also be included in the storytelling around SFSCs because it may be interesting for a wider audience. This was followed by another participant who saw opportunities for promotion of food products that are connected to a specific territory, either through raw materials or traditional methods, the geographical indications. Some local products and regions may be able to grow if they can make these regional traditions part of their marketing strategy. Geographical indications can offer new opportunities for SFSCs.

The discussion on (health) claims also led to a wider discussion on the need for validation and certification of SFSC products. It was argued that this may not just be a question of missing information but maybe even false information. In conventional supply chains, controls, quality assurance and certification (through third parties) can be done at lower cost, but this is much more difficult in SFSCs. Support and funding would facilitate the adoption of quality systems and control by producers involved in SFSCs. In addition, to make it easier for consumers to identify SFSC products, there may be a need for a better definition of what a SFSC is, and for a legal framework.

A final discussion point revolved around the governance of the food system. This relates back to the question of barriers to SFSC development also, as it is not enough to improve public awareness towards sustainable food and to improve skills of producers, for example, but a sustainable food system also requires proper governance. This governance should offer the right framework to stimulate cooperation (between chain actors / stakeholders). For instance, the concept of ‘food councils’ was put forward as a way of including citizens in the governance of the food system and the creation of policies around food at the local level.

Figure 8: Proposed marketing and USP strategy for SFSCs

The above figure illustrates the proposed marketing strategy co-designed with SRG members. Four axes are considered for this strategy: (i) target audience – targeted and untargeted strategy (green cells), (ii) channels and platforms used to convey the message more effectively to the audience (orange cells), (iii) the content of messages delivered and USPs offered to customer segments (blue cells) and finally (iv) who should be involved in strategy development (mint green cells – bottom of the graph).

3. Concluding remarks

The pan-European workshop led to additional reflection on the outcomes of the regional co-creation workshops. The workshop was concluded by informing the participants about the next steps in the project and an invitation for their continued contributions. Participants were also invited to join the MAP Forum on which discussions will be initiated on the agroBRIDGES website. The presentations of the workshop and a feedback form are shared with the participants after the workshop.